

The Role of Health Information Package Programmes in Anaemia Management During Pregnancy

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ABSTRACT

Despite various intervention programmes put in place to reduce pregnancy anaemia in Ghana, there is still a report of high anaemia prevalence in pregnant women receiving antenatal care in Greater Accra of Ghana. Anaemia in pregnancy is a universal public health problem resulting in maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. Antenatal care services alone cannot address anaemia risk in pregnancy, as such there is a need to develop effective health promotion and preventive strategies to reduce anaemia and its associated complications in pregnant women. The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of Health Information Package Programmes (HIPP) in anaemia management during pregnancy. Although there are several ways to conduct interventions to reduce anaemia in pregnancy, the study focused on four key components thus; health worker education, nutrition education, use of contraceptives and Water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH), through effective educational strategies to help increase service providers and pregnant women's knowledge concerning anaemia in pregnancy. Furthermore, the study seeks to promote awareness of better nutrition, infection prevention and family planning, leading to anaemia reduction in pregnancy.

Keywords: Health education, pregnant women, health information and anaemia

1. Introduction

Anaemia in pregnancy remains a global health crisis with its adverse impact, especially on children and pregnant women (Ezirim et al., 2024a). The prevalence rate of anaemia in South and Southeast Asian expectant mothers is 52% and 47% in non-pregnant women (Sunuwar et al., 2020). Anaemia in pregnancy has an association with educational and economic factors. It is also correlated with the following complications, premature delivery and low birth weight babies. Also, the main nutritional contributors to pregnancy outcomes are iron, folate, and vitamin B12 (El-Kholy et al., 2023).

Anaemia is defined as a deficit of red blood cell count or a minimum blood level concentration (Pullakhandam & McRoy, 2024). Pregnant women with haemoglobin levels less than 11.0 g/dL in the first trimester and less than 10.5 or 11.0 g/dL in the second trimester of pregnancy are termed anaemia. (James, 2021). In the year 2019, approximately half a billion women in their fertile age and children between 6–59 months, thus 269 million were reported to have suffered from anaemia Worldwide (Hess et al., 2023; Nirala et al., 2023).

The global cause of anaemia is iron deficiency, other nutritional deficiencies such as vitamin B12, folate, and magnesium can also cause anaemia (Qasrawi et al., 2024). Anaemia is classified by the number of disorders in the red blood cell, with those that impede erythrocyte production. Also, anaemia occurs due to disorders in the maturation of erythrocytes, haemoglobin production, genetic development defects and loss of erythrocytes (Hussien et al., 2023). Anaemia may present signs and symptoms, such as headache, conjunctival and palmar pallor, difficulty in breathing, fatigue, and palpitations (Hayes & Pobischan, 2024; Howard et al., 2024). In clinical practice, the determinant of haemoglobin levels is cardinal in the classification of anaemia (Garcia-Casal et al., 2023).

Anaemia in pregnant women is a major threat to maternal and perinatal outcomes including cesarean section, preterm birth, blood transfusion, postpartum haemorrhage, and infections (Okunade et al., 2024). Its direct consequences affect the health of pregnant women, approximately 32 million globally, and 56% of expectant mothers in developing countries had anaemia in pregnancy. Furthermore, anaemia in pregnant women contributes to low productivity, delays intellectual development, and affects economic status. Interventions to promote and improve anaemia in pregnancy are critical to reduce maternal and perinatal death (J. Zhang et al., 2022).

In Ghana, 70.0% of expectant mothers were anaemic in the year 2008 but sharply declined to 44.6% in 2014. The difference of 25.4% decrease has been attributed to effective intervention programmes on nutrition counselling, iron-folic acid supplementation, infection prevention and treatment of helminths, food fortification and supplementation, family planning services, and women's empowerment among others (Agbozo et al., 2020). Furthermore, the decrease has also come about as a result of; free delivery of insecticide-treated nets, health education at the antenatal

clinics, screening and management of anaemia, hypertension and diabetes, iron supplementation, intermittent prophylaxis treatment for malaria (IPTp) with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (Ayensu et al., 2020).

Despite these intervention programmes implemented to decrease anaemia prevalence in pregnancy, there is still an upsurge of anaemia in expectant mothers (Andoh, 2024). However, anaemia during pregnancy is a major health problem in underdeveloped countries, including Ghana. Therefore, urgent and proper awareness and educational programmes are essential to reduce the rates of anaemia among pregnant women. The study, thus, seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of Health Information Package Programmes (HIPP) in anaemia management during pregnancy.

2. Iron deficiency anaemia during pregnancy

The prevalence of anaemia in pregnant women worldwide is about 41.8% (Ezirim et al., 2024b). The total iron needed during pregnancy is a considerably larger amount than in women who are not pregnant (Das et al., 2024). Iron deficiency anaemia (IDA) has been proven to be the only nutrient deficit that is very common in advanced, low and middle-income countries, distressing especially for women and children (Raut et al., 2022). The upsurge of iron in pregnancy is essential to augment the required fetoplacental unit needed to increase maternal red blood cell mass, and to replace the iron loss during childbirth (Garzon et al., 2020). IDA is a micronutrient deficiency that occurs in pregnancy with its associated complications such as preterm birth, decreased cognitive development, spontaneous abortion, intrauterine fetal death, Infections, low birth weight, hypertension, perinatal morbidity and mortality (Q. Zhang et al., 2021).

The first line of choice in the management of iron deficiency anaemia in pregnancy is the administration of oral iron supplements (Pandey et al., 2024). However, adherence and compliance are a major challenge because of nausea and vomiting in early pregnancy, and abdominal discomfort, which could be aggravated by the intake of iron supplements, which restrain pregnant women from intake. Considering the hindrances, encouraging dietary consumption by refining the quality of food and its diversity, will be an appropriate strategy to improve compliance (Skolmowska et al., 2022).

Expectant mothers at risk of iron deficiency anaemia, should be identified early, ideally at the antenatal visit, through detailed history taken and examination. Healthcare professionals should be aware of risk factors such as teenage pregnancy, history of previous anaemia, multiple pregnancies and short birth interval (less than 1 year) (Benson et al., 2021).

Iron deficiency anaemia in pregnancy can have a significant adverse impact on the mother and foetus (Faruk et al., 2024). Considering the numerous consequences of the disease, addressing iron deficiency anaemia in pregnancy will require an integrated approach, including intensifying awareness and health education at the various service delivery points, early identification and treatment of clinical conditions, developing a well-structured algorithm for diagnosing and

treatment of IDA in pregnancy for service providers and also incorporate anaemia awareness in our national health celebrations to combat anaemia in pregnancy.

3. Knowledge of pregnant women on anaemia prevention interventions

Pregnancy anaemia harms both the mother and foetus. To reduce this adverse outcome, better knowledge and understanding of danger signs in pregnancy is a determinant factor for the expectant mother (Wulandari & Laksono, 2020). Oechsle et al. (2020), their findings indicated that health-seeking behaviour in pregnant women is determined by their understanding and source of health information and how and where to access it. Lifestyle-related health behaviours such as alcohol abuse, coffee intake, medication, oral health, and physical activity in pregnancy have a devastating effect on the health status of the baby and mother (Swami & Ramawat, 2024). Furthermore, the reduction of anaemia in pregnancy is one of the key components of safe motherhood (Dey, 2024). The danger signs of anaemia in pregnancy are numerous and complex, as such it is imperative for pregnant women to have knowledge and understanding of risk factors associated with anaemia in pregnancy. Better health education and understanding will help pregnant women adhere to and comply with government intervention programmes tailored to address anaemia in pregnancy and its consequences (Sinha et al., 2021). Pregnant women with lower levels of education have higher chances of developing anaemia in pregnancy with its resultant effect of low birth weight babies, neonatal death, and preterm babies (Helegbe et al., 2023). Appropriate intervention strategies are recommended by incorporating healthy dietary practices taking into consideration cultural norms (AlAbedi et al., 2020).

Pregnant women's knowledge and understanding of pregnancy anaemia depends on their level of education, income status, beliefs and cultural norms and availability and accessibility of health information (Balcha et al., 2023). Urgent attention is needed to develop standard protocol guidelines and interventions to promote proper nutritional habits in pregnant women to improve their knowledge, adherence, and compliance with anaemia preventive measures. Also improving the reduction of anaemia in pregnancy involves empowering women, creating public awareness, and stakeholder engagement with leaders at various levels to reduce pregnancy anaemia (Purba & Sitepu, 2023).

4. Health Services Provided for Pregnant Mother

Effective antenatal care services organized for pregnant women should consist of three main components (1) client assessment comprising of history taking, physical examination, and laboratory investigations, (2) health promotion including nutrition counselling, birth preparedness, pregnancy education, family planning and immunization (3) care provision involves tetanus toxoid vaccination, psychosocial support, and recordkeeping of vital information about the client. The following services are also rendered thus, checking of blood pressure, iron supplementation, checking of body weight, education and counselling on danger signs in pregnancy, though the components may differ in various countries (Tadesse Berehe & Modibia, 2020). Frequent antenatal

care visits have a significant positive impact on pregnant women's interest and satisfaction than women who make fewer visits. To ensure early detection of danger signs in pregnancy, the antenatal care model recommends a minimum of eight contacts with health service providers, however pregnant women in developing countries especially, do not receive the required number of visits to reduce maternal complications such as maternal morbidity and mortality (Warri & George, 2020). To bridge the gaps contributing to the three delays preventing pregnant women from getting proper and timely health care during pregnancy, it's essential to promote and improve access to skilled delivery, most importantly at the lower levels of healthcare. The accessibility and utilization of health services by pregnant women are determined not only by the quality of services provided but also by clients' perceptions and experiences (Ope, 2020).

Figure 1: A model for evaluating the quality of health service delivery in pregnancy (Ope, 2020).

Figure 1 above, illustrates the approach and determinant factors in providing quality care services to pregnant women. The provision of quality care to expectant mothers depends on the provision of care, the perception and experience of the client are vital in improving health. Health interventions can be carried out effectively based on a better understanding of quality healthcare services and the client's perception and experience of quality care. Taking into consideration barriers in seeking healthcare and focus areas for health interventions (Ope, 2020)

Quality health service delivery to pregnant women is very important, especially in antenatal care. Considering the consequences of developing pregnancy anaemia, comprehensive interventions; comprising education, access to quality health care, and clarifying misconceptions about myths and taboos related to pregnancy and nutrition by service providers will help provide holistic healthcare to pregnant mothers. Establishing prenatal courses and pregnancy schools in various facilities and communities will also help to address knowledge gaps and improve maternal

healthcare usage. In other to address these challenges associated with the management and prevention of anaemia in pregnancy, there should be well well-structured system to benefit both clients and service providers. Addressing staff attrition, provision of needed logistics for health workers, accommodation complex, healthy environment for clients and modification of cultural values. These will motivate health workers to work hard and improve services and antenatal coverage leading to good health and reduction of anaemia in pregnancy.

5. Health information package programmes in anaemia during pregnancy

Anaemia in pregnancy remains a major global health problem in developing countries especially, contributing to negative impacts for the pregnant mother and baby. Several strategies and intervention programmes have been implemented to address this issue, including increasing pregnant women's knowledge about anaemia, iron and folic acid supplementation (Arifah et al., 2023).

A health information package programme (HIPP) is termed a coordinated programme which involves planned education and various health interventions including anaemia in pregnant women and its prevention (Elsharkawy et al., 2022). The efficiency of the health education, supplemented by regular follow-ups via WhatsApp helps significantly to improve knowledge, food selection, compliance, and haemoglobin levels in pregnant mothers receiving routine care. Hence the combination of educational interventions with digital follow-ups enhances better outcomes in anaemic pregnant women (Elsharkawy et al, 2022).

Community-based health education by utilizing community health volunteers to deliver iron and folic acid supplementation (IFAS) also increases maternal IFAS knowledge and significantly enhances positive attitudes towards IFAS (Kamau et, al. 2019). Arifah et al. (2023), also affirmed that daily educational messages on anaemia prevention, behaviour, and knowledge help to improve anaemia-related outcomes in pregnant women and intensify health education on early detection and management of anaemia. This study, thus, seeks to assess the effectiveness and efficiency of Health Information Package Programmes (HIPP) in anaemia management during pregnancy. Four key components including Health worker education, nutrition education, promoting birth spacing and use of contraceptives and Water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) are areas of interest in terms of health education to both the service providers and pregnant women to reduce anaemia in pregnancy.

Figure 2: Conceptual framework for Reducing Anaemia in Pregnancy using Health Information Package programmes.

The figure above shows how the four key components that help to reduce anaemia in pregnancy are interrelated. Health worker education, nutrition education, use of contraceptives and water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) in Figure 1 above, are conceptualized as intervention programmes in creating awareness and health educational activities for both service providers and pregnant women to mitigate anaemia with its associated complications in pregnancy.

Health worker education

Periodic refresher training for service providers is cardinal to enhance knowledge and skills on high-risk pregnancy conditions, nutrition in pregnancy, birth spacing, infection prevention and promote awareness about long-term complications in pregnancy. Also, a Pregnancy app can be developed and applied in the various service delivery points focusing on two main components, (1) Health education and training for service providers on anaemia in pregnancy, nutrition, contraceptive use and infection prevention. (2) Offering technical guidelines, medical decision support and lifestyle education for service providers through training on the app (Hirst et al., 2023)

Nutritional education

Nutrition plays an essential part in pregnancy and the development of the foetus (Meyyazhagan et al., 2023). The role of optimal nutrition begins before conception, during pregnancy, delivery, and post-delivery (Han et al., 2023). Extending via infant and adolescence, nutrition in pregnancy has received very minimum interest and attention from various studies (Marshall et al., 2022). To improve dietary intake, there is a need to promote the use of locally accessible nutrient-dense foods for pregnant women (Katenga-Kaunda et al., 2020). Nutrition education to pregnant women should be communicated in their local language and educational materials should also be developed and modified in their local context to suit their environment. Pregnant women should also be provided with hard copies of educational materials for self-learning including anaemia definition, signs and symptoms of anaemia, anaemia causes, complications of anaemia, lifestyle, nutrition and prevention and management of anaemia (Munyogwa et al., 2021).

Promoting birth spacing and the use of contraceptives

Contraception methods are important to prevent unwanted pregnancies and sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) (Siddiqui et al., 2020). Family planning promotes gender equality by offering women the opportunities to prevent unwanted menstruation, breastfeeding, and promote health. An increase in the number of pregnancies accounts for an upsurge in the number of miscarriages and maternal deaths owing to numerous risk factors such as increased preterm babies, and further obstetric complications (Siddiqui et al., 2020). The increase in fertility rate in Sub-Saharan Africa has re-strengthened global awareness and interventions in family planning to improve maternal health. Collective efforts to improve family planning are aimed at women, as they are mostly affected by obstetric and pregnancy complications and are also the main users of family planning methods (Kibira et al., 2020). Birth spacing effectively helps women recover from preceding pregnancies (Pimentel et al., 2020). Family planning awareness on the accessible and various types and methods assist women in making informed choices in terms of adherence, and also fertility preferences (Shah et al., 2021). Pregnant women need to be well educated on the various family planning methods that can help reduce anaemia in pregnancy. Family planning preferences are linked with anaemia, possibly helping reduce menstrual blood loss. Hormonal contraceptives like Depo-medroxyprogesterone acetate (DMPA) have been researched to decrease anaemia consequences (Aboagye et al, 2023). DMPA can affect the transient interruption of menstrual flow in a lot of family planning acceptors (Bastianelli et al., 2020). Decreasing the flow of menses may help users conserve their haemoglobin and iron stores (Steller et al., 2021). Women who receive family planning services have less chance of developing anaemia compared with women who do not use any form of contraceptive in their reproductive age. Furthermore, users of family planning commodities such as combined oral contraceptive pills (COCP) can regulate the menstrual cycle in women by thinning the endometrium and hence, reducing the risk of excessive menstrual flow, thereby reducing anaemia in women in their fertility age (Aboagye et al, 2023). Women in their fertility age have a higher risk of developing iron deficiency anaemia, as such, the combination of

contraceptive commodities with iron supplements can reduce the chances of developing iron deficiency anaemia thereby increasing haemoglobin levels and improving maternal health (Fischer et al., 2021).

Water, sanitation, and hygiene

The basic human rights that reinforce the essential basic needs of life are water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) (Pereira et al., 2024). Primarily to ensure the following basic needs such as nutrition, excretion, safety, dignity, productivity, and happiness are met. However, a lot of people, especially in developing countries, do not have potable water at home and lack access to sanitation facilities (Chirgwin et al., 2021). Eventually, this results in gastrointestinal infections like diarrhoea, acute respiratory tract infections, and diminished nutrition causing anaemia, especially for vulnerable groups, particularly women and girls (Chirgwin et al., 2021). The deprivation of supply of water for domestic purposes can have great consequences on maternal and neonatal health, compromising the condition of the water taken by expectant mothers, and causing infections as a result of deprived access to good sanitation (Cameron et al., 2021).

Figure 3: Conceptual framework connecting water, sanitation, and hygiene using Maternal and Reproductive Health (Campbell et al., 2015)

Figure 3 above reviews the various means by which water, sanitation and hygiene(WASH) result in disease conditions and complications, which can be classified into two main dimensions: (i) in water, bacteria, or compounds in water and (ii) behaviour because of social, cultural, and environmental factors linked to WASH, affecting good health in women, pregnant women, foetuses or infants. The development of this framework associates four fundamental routes through which water can spread diseases, thus water-based, water-borne, water-washed, and water-related (Campbell et al., 2015). These classifications can contribute to airborne transmission, chemical contaminants, and insect vector transmission. Figure 3 gives a summary of the health implications of these routes of transmission to the mother and foetus (Campbell et al., 2015).

6. Conclusion

Anaemia intervention programmes in pregnancy are factored into various sectoral action plans, but ineffective implementation is a major hindrance accounting for discrepancies relating to anaemia strategies and outcomes. Health information package programmes incorporating health worker education, nutrition education, use of contraceptives, Water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH), through appropriate educational interventions, coordinated programmes, community-based strategies, and mobile health can efficiently increase awareness, compliance, and resultant increase in haemoglobin levels in expectant mothers with anaemia. Furthermore, well-structured educational programmes for both service providers and pregnant women are key to increasing their knowledge regarding anaemia in pregnancy. This will go a long way to promote better nutrition, infection prevention and contraceptive choices, resulting in anaemia reduction in pregnancy.

References

- Aboagye, R. G., Okyere, J., Seidu, A.-A., Ahinkorah, B. O., Budu, E., & Yaya, S. (2023). Relationship between the history of hormonal contraceptive use and anaemia status among women in sub-Saharan Africa: A large population-based study. *Plos One*, *18*(6), e0286392.
- Abujilban, S., Hatamleh, R., & Al-Shuqerat, S. (2019). The impact of a planned health educational program on the compliance and knowledge of Jordanian pregnant women with anaemia. *Women & Health*, *59*(7), 748–759. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03630242.2018.1549644>
- Agbozo, F., Abubakari, A., Der, J., & Jahn, A. (2020). Maternal dietary intakes, red blood cell indices and risk for anaemia in the first, second and third trimesters of pregnancy and at pre-delivery. *Nutrients*, *12*(3), 777.
- AlAbedi, G. A., Arar, A. A., & Alridh, M. S. A. (2020). Assessment of pregnant women's knowledge and practices concerning iron deficiency anaemia at Al-Amara City/Iraq. *Medico-Legal Update*, *20*(3), 151.
- Andoh, J. (2024). Nutritional Interventions and Anaemia Prevention in Pregnancy: A Comprehensive Review. *Korean Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*, *28*(1), 350–363.
- Arifah, I., Pambarep, T. A., Khoiriyah, L., Kusumaningrum, T. I., Werdani, K., & Ngadiyono, N. (2023). Effectiveness of daily educational message on pregnancy anaemia prevention behaviour and knowledge: A pilot randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, *12*(1), 296. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_108_23

- Ayensu, J., Annan, R., Lutterodt, H., Edusei, A., & Peng, L. S. (2020). Prevalence of anaemia and low intake of dietary nutrients in pregnant women living in rural and urban areas in the Ashanti region of Ghana. *Plos One*, *15*(1), e0226026.
- Balcha, W. F., Eteffa, T., Arega Tesfu, A., & Abeje Alemayehu, B. (2023). Maternal Knowledge of Anemia and Adherence to its Prevention Strategies: A Health Facility-Based Cross-Sectional Study Design. *INQUIRY: The Journal of Health Care Organization, Provision, and Financing*, *60*, 00469580231167731.
- Bastianelli, C., Farris, M., Bruni, V., Rosato, E., Brosens, I., & Benagiano, G. (2020). Effects of progestin-only contraceptives on the endometrium. *Expert Review of Clinical Pharmacology*, *13*(10), 1103–1123.
- Benson, C., Shah, A., Stanworth, S., Frise, C., Spiby, H., Lax, S., Murray, J., & Klein, A. (2021). The effect of iron deficiency and anaemia on women's health. *Anaesthesia*, *76*, 84–95.
- Cameron, L., Chase, C., & Suarez, D. C. (2021). Relationship between water and sanitation and maternal health: Evidence from Indonesia. *World Development*, *147*, 105637.
- Campbell, O. M., Benova, L., Gon, G., Afsana, K., & Cumming, O. (2015). Getting the basic rights—the role of water, sanitation and hygiene in maternal and reproductive health: A conceptual framework. *Tropical Medicine & International Health*, *20*(3), 252–267.
- Chirgwin, H., Cairncross, S., Zehra, D., & Sharma Waddington, H. (2021). Interventions promoting uptake of water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) technologies in low and middle-income countries: An evidence and gap map of effectiveness studies. *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, *17*(4), e1194.
- Das, P., Das, T., Das, P., & Roy, T. (2024). An association of deficiencies in balanced dietary practices and inadequate iron and folic acid supplement intake during pregnancy and increasing risk of pre-eclampsia or eclampsia among Indian women. *PLOS Global Public Health*, *4*(1), e0001633.
- Dey, M. P. (2024). MANAGEMENT OF ANAEMIA IN PREGNANCY. *SAFE MOTHERHOOD AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN THE CONTEMPORARY PERSPECTIVE: SAFE MOTHERHOOD AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE*, 41.
- El-Kholy, A. A., El Kholy, E. A., Abdou, A. H., Karar, H. A. D., Bushara, M. A., Abdelaal, K., & Sayed, R. (2023). Prevalence and associated factors of anaemia among pregnant women and the impact of clinical pharmacist counselling on their awareness level: A cross-sectional study. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*, *31*(8), 101699.
- Elsharkawy, N. B., Abdelaziz, E. M., Ouda, M. M., & Oraby, F. A. (2022). Effectiveness of Health Information Package Program on Knowledge and Compliance among Pregnant Women with Anemia: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *19*(5), 2724.
- Ezirim, E., Anele, D., Okite, U., Abali, I., Akwuruoha, E., Onyemereze, C., Omole, O., & Airaodion, A. (2024a). Awareness, Prevalence and Severity of Anaemia and Related Contributing Factors, among Pregnant Women Attending Antenatal Clinic in a Teaching Hospital in Southern Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Pregnancy and Childbirth*, *7*(1), 38–52.
- Ezirim, E., Anele, D., Okite, U., Abali, I., Akwuruoha, E., Onyemereze, C., Omole, O., & Airaodion, A. (2024b). Awareness, Prevalence and Severity of Anaemia and Related Contributing Factors, among Pregnant Women Attending Antenatal Clinic in a Teaching Hospital in Southern Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Pregnancy and Childbirth*, *7*(1), 38–52.
- Faruk, S., Sanusi, K. O., Ibrahim, K. G., Abubakar, B., Malami, I., Bello, M. B., Abubakar, M. B., Abbas, A. Y., & Imam, M. U. (2024). Age and sex-based impacts of maternal iron deficiency on offspring's cognitive function and anaemia: A systematic review. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 1–9.
- Fischer, J. A., Sasai, C. S., & Karakochuk, C. D. (2021). Iron-containing oral contraceptives and their effect on haemoglobin and biomarkers of iron status: A narrative review. *Nutrients*, *13*(7), 2340.
- Garcia-Casal, M. N., Dary, O., Jefferds, M. E., & Pasricha, S. (2023). Diagnosing anaemia: Challenges selecting methods, addressing underlying causes, and implementing actions at the public health level. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, *1524*(1), 37–50.
- Garzon, S., Cacciato, P. M., Certelli, C., Salvaggio, C., Magliarditi, M., & Rizzo, G. (2020). Iron deficiency anaemia in pregnancy: Novel approaches for an old problem. *Oman Medical Journal*, *35*(5), e166.

- Han, S. M., Huang, F., Derraik, J. G., Vickers, M. H., Devaraj, S., Redeuil, K., Campos-Giménez, E., Pang, W. W., Godfrey, K. M., & Chan, S.-Y. (2023). A nutritional supplement during preconception and pregnancy increases human milk vitamin D but not B-vitamin concentrations. *Clinical Nutrition*, 42(12), 2443–2456.
- Hayes, A., & Pobischan, A. (2024). *Crash Course Paediatrics: For UKMLA and Medical Exams*. Elsevier Health Sciences.
- Helegbe, G. K., Aryee, P., & Mohammed, B. S. (2023). Preterm Delivery and Neonatal Deaths among Anaemic Pregnant Women in the Bolgatanga Metropolis of Ghana. *Anemia*, 2023.
- Hess, S. Y., Owais, A., Jefferds, M. E. D., Young, M. F., Cahill, A., & Rogers, L. M. (2023). Accelerating action to reduce anaemia: Review of causes and risk factors and related data needs. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1523(1), 11–23.
- Hirst, J. E., Votruba, N., Billot, L., Arora, V., Rajan, E., Thout, S. R., Peiris, D., Patel, A., Norton, R., & Mullins, E. (2023). A community-based intervention to improve screening, referral and follow-up of non-communicable diseases and anaemia amongst pregnant and postpartum women in rural India: Study protocol for a cluster randomised trial. *Trials*, 24(1), 510.
- Howard, R., Al-Mayhany, T., Carr, A., Leff, A., Morrow, J., & Rossor, A. (2024). Toxic, metabolic and physical insults to the nervous system. *Neurology: A Queen Square Textbook*, 903–943.
- Hussien, R. S., Jabuk, S. I., Altaee, Z. M., & Al-Maamori, A. M. (2023). *REVIEW OF ANEMIA: TYPES AND CAUSES*.
- James, A. H. (2021). Iron deficiency anaemia in pregnancy. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 138(4), 663–674.
- Kamau, M., Mirie, W., Kimani, S., & Mugoya, I. (2019). Effect of community-based health education on knowledge and attitude towards iron and folic acid supplementation among pregnant women in Kiambu County, Kenya: A quasi-experimental study. *PLOS ONE*, 14(11), e0224361.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0224361>
- Katenga-Kaunda, L. Z., Iversen, P. O., Holmboe-Ottesen, G., Fjeld, H., Mdala, I., & Kamudoni, P. R. (2020). Dietary intake and processes of behaviour change in a nutrition education intervention for pregnant women in rural Malawi: A cluster-randomised controlled trial. *Public Health Nutrition*, 23(13), 2345–2354.
- Kibira, S. P., Karp, C., Wood, S. N., Desta, S., Galadanci, H., Makumbi, F. E., Omoluabi, E., Shiferaw, S., Seme, A., & Tsui, A. (2020). Covert use of contraception in three sub-Saharan African countries: A qualitative exploration of motivations and challenges. *BMC Public Health*, 20, 1–10.
- Marshall, N. E., Abrams, B., Barbour, L. A., Catalano, P., Christian, P., Friedman, J. E., Hay Jr, W. W., Hernandez, T. L., Krebs, N. F., & Oken, E. (2022). The importance of nutrition in pregnancy and lactation: Lifelong consequences. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 226(5), 607–632.
- Meyyazhagan, A., Bhotla, H. K., Tsibizova, V., Pappuswamy, M., Chaundhary, A., Arumugam, V. A., Al Qasem, M., & Di Renzo, G. C. (2023). Nutrition paves the way to environmental toxicants and influences fetal development during pregnancy. *Best Practice & Research Clinical Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, 102351.
- Munyogwa, M. J., Gibore, N. S., Ngowi, A. F., & Mwampagatwa, I. H. (2021). Effect of nutritional education intervention to reduce anaemia during pregnancy in Dodoma City, Tanzania: Protocol for a cluster randomized controlled trial. *Biology Methods and Protocols*, 6(1), bpab012.
- Nirala, S. K., Rao, R., Naik, B. N., Patil, S., Verma, M., Singh, C., & Pandey, S. (2023). Anaemia—a scourge to maternal and child development in Bihar, India. *European Journal of Clinical and Experimental Medicine*, 2, 416–423.
- Oechsle, A., Wensing, M., Ullrich, C., & Bombana, M. (2020). Health knowledge of lifestyle-related risks during pregnancy: A cross-sectional study of pregnant women in Germany. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(22), 8626.
- Okunade, K. S., Adejimi, A. A., Olumodeji, A. M., Olowe, A., Oyedeji, O. A., Ademuyiwa, I. Y., Adelabu, H., Toks-Omage, E., Okoro, A. C., & Davies, N. (2024). Prenatal anaemia and risk of postpartum haemorrhage: A cohort analysis of data from the Predict-PPH study. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1), 1–10.
- Ope, B. W. (2020). Reducing maternal mortality in Nigeria: Addressing maternal health services' perception and experience. *Journal of Global Health Reports*, 4, e2020028.

- Pandey, A. K., Gautam, D., Tolani, H., & Neogi, S. B. (2024). Clinical outcome post-treatment of anaemia in pregnancy with intravenous versus oral iron therapy: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Scientific Reports*, *14*(1), 179.
- Pereira, C. T., Sorlini, S., Sátiro, J., & Albuquerque, A. (2024). *Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) in Schools: A Catalyst for Upholding Human Rights to Water and Sanitation in Anápolis, Brazil*.
- Pimentel, J., Ansari, U., Omer, K., Gidado, Y., Baba, M. C., Andersson, N., & Cockcroft, A. (2020). Factors associated with a short birth interval in low-and middle-income countries: A systematic review. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, *20*, 1–17.
- Pullakhandam, S., & McRoy, S. (2024). Classification and Explanation of Iron Deficiency Anemia from Complete Blood Count Data Using Machine Learning. *BioMedInformatics*, *4*(1), 661–672.
- Purba, T., & Sitepu, L. P. (2023). Analysis of Factors Influencing Anemia Prevalence in Pregnant Women: A Study in the Berastagi Community Health Center Working Area. *Acta Psychologia*, *2*(3), 98–106.
- Qasrawi, R., Badrasawi, M., Al-Halawa, D. A., Polo, S. V., Khader, R. A., Al-Taweel, H., Alwafa, R. A., Zahdeh, R., Hahn, A., & Schuchardt, J. P. (2024). Identification and prediction of association patterns between nutrient intake and anaemia using machine learning techniques: Results from a cross-sectional study with university female students from Palestine. *European Journal of Nutrition*, 1–15.
- Raut, A. K., Hiwale, K. M., & Hiwale, K. (2022). Iron deficiency anaemia in pregnancy. *Cureus*, *14*(9).
- Shah, A. M., Lee, K., & Nisa Mir, J. (2021). Exploring readiness for birth control in improving women health status: Factors influencing the adoption of modern contraceptive methods for family planning practices. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *18*(22), 11892.
- Siddiqui, M., Fatima, K., Ali, S. N., Fatima, M., Naveed, W., Siddiqui, F., Naqvi, T., Khan, S., Amin, M., & Liaquat, A. (2020). Prevalence and predictors of contraception usage in Karachi, Pakistan. *Cureus*, *12*(10).
- Sinha, A., Adhikary, M., Phukan, J. P., Kedia, S., & Sinha, T. (2021). A study on anaemia and its risk factors among pregnant women attending the antenatal clinic of a rural medical college of West Bengal. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, *10*(3), 1327–1331.
- Skolmowska, D., Głąbska, D., Kołota, A., & Guzek, D. (2022). Effectiveness of dietary interventions in prevention and treatment of iron-deficiency anaemia in pregnant women: A systematic review of randomized controlled trials. *Nutrients*, *14*(15), 3023.
- Steller, J. G., Blue, R., Zahner, C., Frisch, E. H., Bayuse, T., Auñon-Chancellor, S., & Jennings, R. T. (2021). Menstrual management considerations in the space environment. *Reach*, *23*, 100044.
- Sunuwar, D. R., Singh, D. R., Chaudhary, N. K., Pradhan, P. M. S., Rai, P., & Tiwari, K. (2020). Prevalence and factors associated with anaemia among women of reproductive age in seven South and Southeast Asian countries: Evidence from nationally representative surveys. *PloS One*, *15*(8), e0236449.
- Swami, R., & Ramawat, B. (2024). Clinical understanding of Garbhini Paricharya: Routine care for pregnant women through Ayurveda. *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrated Medical Sciences*, *9*(2), 213–220.
- Tadesse Berehe, T., & Modibia, L. M. (2020). Assessment of quality of antenatal care services and its determinant factors in public health facilities of Hossana Town, Hadiya Zone, Southern Ethiopia: A longitudinal study. *Advances in Public Health*, *2020*, 1–11.
- Warri, D., & George, A. (2020). Perceptions of pregnant women of reasons for late initiation of antenatal care: A qualitative interview study. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, *20*, 1–12.
- Wulandari, R. D., & Laksono, A. D. (2020). Determinants of knowledge of pregnancy danger signs in Indonesia. *PLoS One*, *15*(5), e0232550.
- Zhang, J., Li, Q., Song, Y., Fang, L., Huang, L., & Sun, Y. (2022). Nutritional factors for anaemia in pregnancy: A systematic review with meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Public Health*, *10*, 1041136.
- Zhang, Q., Lu, X.-M., Zhang, M., Yang, C.-Y., Lv, S.-Y., Li, S.-F., Zhong, C.-Y., & Geng, S.-S. (2021). Adverse effects of iron deficiency anaemia on pregnancy outcome and offspring development and intervention of three iron supplements. *Scientific Reports*, *11*(1), 1347.